

LOW POWER CMOS FULL ADDER DESIGN WITH 12 TRANSISTORS

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ABSTRACT

In present work two new designs for single bit full adders have been presented using three transistors XOR gates. Adder having twelve transistors shows power consumption of 1274 μ W with maximum output delay of 0.2049ns. Power consumption and maximum output delay shows variation [1274 - 141.77] μ W & [0.2049 - 0.4167] ns with varying supply voltage from [3.3 - 1.8] V. Further, reverse body bias technique for power reduction has been applied to adder. Adder with reverse body bias shows power consumption variations of [1270 - 1067.60] μ W with varying NMOS reverse bias from [0.0 to - 2.0] V. Delay of adder shows variations [0.2049 - 0.2316] ns with reverse bias variation [0.0 to 2.0] V. Simulations have been carried out at different supply voltage with increasing reverse biased applied to NMOS transistor and results shows improvements in power consumption of adder. A comparison with earlier reported circuits have been presented and proposed circuit's shows less power dissipation.

KEYWORDS

CMOS, Exclusive-OR (XOR), full adder, low power design and reverse body bias.

1. INTRODUCTION

With continuous increase in complexity and number of components on integrated circuits, power consumption of VLSI (very large scale integration) circuits is increasing at a rapid rate. The demand and popularity of hand held battery operated devices further added research efforts in the field of low power CMOS design. Large power consumption affects the circuit operation and reliability by increasing temperature of circuits. Packaging and cooling costs of VLSI system also goes up with increase in power consumptions. Three major source of power consumption exists in CMOS circuits: 1) switching power due to output transitions 2) short circuit power due to current between V_{DD} and ground during switching 3) static power due to leakage and static currents. Full adders being core building blocks in different VLSI circuits like comparators, parity checkers, compressors. Performance of adder circuit highly affects the overall capability of the system. Improvement in performance of full adder in terms of power consumption, delay and other parameters will affect system capability as a whole.

Many logic styles have been used in past for designing the full adder circuits. Standard static CMOS full adder with pull up and pull-down networks used 28 transistors [1]. Complementary pass-transistor logic (CPL) with 32 transistors shows better driving capability but dissipates large power [2]. Transmission gate CMOS adder (TGA) was based on transmission gates and used 20 transistors [3]. Main disadvantage of TGA was that it requires double transistors that of pass transistor logic for implementations same logic function. A transmission function full adder (TFA) was based on transmission function theory and used 16 transistors [4]. A full adder cell implemented with 14 transistor using XOR design and transmission gates [5]. Multiplexer based adder (MBA) used 12 transistors with elimination of direct path to power supply were reported [6]. Static energy recovery full (SERF) adder with 10 transistors with reduced power

consumption at the cost of large delay had been presented [7]. Another design with 10 transistors full adder by using XOR/XNOR gates had been reported [8]. Performance analysis of different tree structured arithmetic circuits had been presented [9]. A hybrid CMOS logic style adder with 22 transistors had been reported [10]. A full adder using 22 transistors based on hybrid pass logic with output drive had been presented [11]. Full adder for embedded applications using three inputs XOR have been reported [12]. A 16 transistor full adder cell with XOR/XNOR, pass transistors and transmission gate have been reported [13]. Structured approach for implementation of single bit full adders using XOR/XNOR has been reported [14] as shown in figure 1. With partitioning the full adder module into minor module, equations (1) and equations (2) can be written as

$$\text{Sum} = H \text{ xor } C_{in} = H \cdot C_{in}' + H' \cdot C_{in} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{out} = A \cdot H' + C_{in} \cdot H \quad (2)$$

Where H is half sum (A xor B) and H' is complement of H.

Figure 1. Structure of single bit full adder

To reduce the standby leakage in CMOS circuits, a reverse body biasing is generally used. Body biasing techniques make use of body terminal bias as another control mechanism to dynamically tune threshold voltages [16]. Threshold voltage (V_{th}) is related by the square root of the bias voltage implying that a significant voltage level would be needed to raise the V_{th} . An optimized design is highly desirable at circuit level to avoid large power dissipation, large delay and to achieve sufficient output level. Here, an energy efficient single bit full adders with 12 transistors using three transistor XOR gate [15], inverters and multiplexer blocks have been presented., which shows better results in term of power dissipation. The paper is organized as follows: In Section II, new single bit full adders using 12 transistors have been reported. In section III results of power consumptions, maximum output delay results for the proposed full adder's cell have been presented and compared with earlier reported circuits. Conclusions have been drawn in Section IV.

2. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

New single bit adders using three transistor XOR gate [15] and multiplexer blocks are presented in this paper. Sum and carry out (C_{out}) are generated by equations (1) and (2). Circuit diagram of first proposed adder (adder-I) with two XOR gates, two inverters and two multiplexers has been shown in figure 2. In Adder-I, C_{out} (carry out) signal has been generated by two transistor multiplexer block with C_{in} , A and XNOR signal. Sum signal is generated with XNOR signal generated by inverter and C_{in} signal. Gate lengths of all transistors have been taken as $0.35\mu\text{m}$. In XOR gates widths of [P1-P4] have been taken as $4.0\mu\text{m}$ whereas width of [N1-N2] has been taken as $0.5\mu\text{m}$. Widths of all NMOS [N3-N6] have been taken as $1.0\mu\text{m}$ whereas widths of [P5-P7] have been taken as $2.5\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 2. Adder-I with 12 transistors

A further improvement in above circuit has been made with reverse body bias. As CMOS inverter is responsible for major portion of power consumption in this adder circuit. Reverse bias voltage (V_1) has been applied to two NMOS [N3 & N4] used in CMOS inverters. Substrate terminal of PMOS [P5 & P6] transistor used in inverter are connected to V_{DD} . By application of reverse body bias, the V_t is increased as given in equation (3), which subsequently reduces the sub threshold leakage currents [16], [17].

$$V_t = V_{t0} + \gamma \left(\sqrt{2\phi_f + V_{sb}} - \sqrt{2\phi_f} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where V_{t0} is threshold voltage for $V_{sb} = 0V$; ϕ_f is Fermi potential and γ is substrate bias coefficient.

Figure 3. Adder-II with reverse body bias

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Simulations have been carried out in SPICE with TSMC 0.35 μ m process technology with supply voltage of 3.3V. Table-I shows results of power consumption and maximum output delay for adder with 12 transistors (adder-I) without reverse body bias. Supply voltage has been varied from [3.3 - 1.8] V and power consumption and maximum output delay results have been obtained. Figure 4 shows power consumption variation for the adder-I with varying supply voltage. Figure 5 show effects of supply voltage on maximum out put delay. Figure 6 shows input and output waveforms results for adder-I with supply voltage of 3.3V.

Table I. Power consumption and maximum out delay for adder-I

Supply voltage (V)	Power consumption (μ W)	Maximum output delay (ns)
3.3	1274.0	0.2049
3.0	957.009	0.2209
2.7	685.141	0.2430
2.4	457.826	0.2744
2.1	274.315	0.3262
1.8	141.776	0.4167

Figure 4. Power consumption variations of adder-I with supply voltage

Figure 5. Output delay variations of adder-I with supply voltage

Figure 6. Input and out waveforms results for adder-I

Table-II shows the power consumption and delay results for adder (adder-II) with reverse body bias. Reverse body bias voltage has been varied from [0.0 to -2.0] V and power consumption and delay values have been obtained. Figure 7(a) & (b) shows power consumption and delay variation with reverse bias voltage for adder-II at 3.3V supply voltage.

Table II. Power consumption and delay with reverse bias for adder-II at 3.3 V supply voltage

Reverse body bias voltage (V)	Power consumption (μ W)	Maximum output delay (ns)
0.0	1274.0	0.2049
-0.2	1252.0	0.2078
-0.4	1229.9	0.2105
-0.6	1207.9	0.2132
-0.8	1185.6	0.2159
-1.0	1164.4	0.2186
-1.2	1143.8	0.2213
-1.4	1123.9	0.2239
-1.6	1104.8	0.2265
-1.8	1086.4	0.2290
-2.0	1067.6	0.2316

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. (a) Power consumption (b) delay variation for adder-II with reverse bias voltage

Figure 8 shows the power consumption variation for adder-II with different supply voltage and it has been observed that power consumption is reduced with increase in reverse bias voltage. Delay variation of adder-II (improved circuit of adder-I) also have been shown in figure 9. Delay is slightly increased with increase in reverse body bias. Figure 10 shows input and out waveforms results for adder-II with reverse bias of -1.0V at supply voltage of 3.3V. Some earlier reported circuits have been simulated in 0.18µm technology with same input parameters and input patterns as for proposed circuits. It has been observed from table IV that proposed circuit gives reduced power consumption with minimum transistors.

Table III. Power consumption and delay of adder-II at different supply voltages

Bias voltage (V)	Supply voltage = 3.0V		Supply voltage = 2.7V		Supply voltage = 2.4V		Supply voltage = 2.1V	
	Power consumption (μW)	Delay (ns)						
-0.0	957.009	0.2209	685.141	0.2430	457.826	0.2744	274.315	0.3262
-0.2	937.726	0.2243	668.210	0.2481	442.565	0.2801	261.489	0.3368
-0.4	918.279	0.2278	651.010	0.2518	427.127	0.2876	251.134	0.3486
-0.6	898.761	0.2313	633.439	0.2572	412.5072	0.2956	242.961	0.3625
-0.8	879.134	0.2347	616.593	0.2613	399.6438	0.3027	236.919	0.3749
-1.0	860.341	0.2383	600.679	0.2663	388.2397	0.3104	232.7321	0.3877
-1.2	842.310	0.2421	585.395	0.2718	378.402	0.3185	230.006	0.4007
-1.4	825.106	0.2457	571.737	0.2771	370.185	0.3261	228.325	0.4140
-1.6	807.928	0.2493	559.072	0.2818	363.132	0.3341	227.328	0.4285
-1.8	792.660	0.2528	547.483	0.2875	358.294	0.3413	226.751	0.4441
-2.0	778.061	0.2559	537.051	0.2928	354.669	0.3530	226.417	0.4586

Figure 8. Power consumption with reverse body bias at different supply voltages

Figure 9. Output delay with reverse body bias at different supply voltages

Figure 10. Input and output waveforms for adder-II with reverse bias of -1.0V at 3.3V supply voltage

Table-IV. Comparison of power consumption with other circuits

Adder configuration	Power consumption(μ W)	Number of transistors for design
TGA20T [4]	1255.54	20
22T hybrid adder [7]	1836.4	22
22T HPSC [11]	1533.9	22
18T [3]	617.23	18
Present work adder-I	1274.0	12
Present work adder-II	1067.6	12

Power efficient adders have been designed with different combination of XOR and XNOR gates and pass transistor multiplexer concept. Power consumption has been reduced further with reverse body biasing of transistors. Reverse body biasing technique provides the way to reduce power consumption without adding any extra hardware on circuit. This work gives new design of single bit full adder with 12 transistors and extends the concept of body bias for optimized adder design. Results show that proper selection of bias voltage reduces the power consumption with little compromise in delay and contribute to overall performance of system.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In reported work two new circuits for single bit full adders have been reported. First circuit designed with 12 transistors shows power consumption of 1274.0 μ W with delay of 0.2049 ns at 3.3V supply voltage. Adder circuit has been improved with reverse body bias technique and gives reduced power consumption. Adder-II shows power consumption variations [1274.0 - 1067.6] μ W of with varying reverse bias voltage from [0.0 to -2.0] V. Delay of adder-II shows variation [0.2049 - 0.2316] ns with varying substrate bias from [0.0 to 2.0] V. Further, power consumption and delay results obtained with different supply voltage shows that power consumption has been improved in adder-II with slight increase in delay. Comparisons with earlier reported circuits show that proposed circuits shows lesser power consumption with reduced transistor count.

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